

LABOR EFFICIENCY – LIFE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT FACTOR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7970849>

Калит сўзлар: меҳнат самарадорлиги, амалдаги меҳнат самарадорлиги”, нақд меҳнат самара-дорлиги, потенциал меҳнат самарадорлиги,ислохотларнинг меҳнат самарадорлигига таъсири, меҳнат самарадорлигини камайтираётган омиллар, меҳнат самарадорлигини ошириш имкониятлари.

Ключевые слова: производительность труда, фактическая производительность труда, наличная производительность труда, потенциальная производительность труда, влияние реформ на производительность труда, факторы, снижающие производительность труда, возможности повышения производительности труда.

Keywords: labor productivity, actual labor productivity, available labor productivity, potential labor productivity, the impact of reforms on labor productivity, factors that reduce labor productivity, opportunities to increase labor productivity.

In our country, large-scale reforms are being carried out aimed at building a new Uzbekistan. "The new Uzbekistan is changing, moving - LABOR EFFICIENCY – LIFE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT is a renewed society that professes peace, a free world. " The primary foundations for building such a society, of course, go into the economy. Given this, the head of state noted: "The new Uzbekistan relies on modernized savings." Because without ensuring a stable pace of economic development, it is impossible to build a new society, to increase the well-being of people. If we come to an economic recovery, scientists and researchers will talk about many factors that provide it. Labor efficiency plays a big role in this series of factors. When accelerating the economic recovery, we must summarize and develop scientific considerations about the essence of labor efficiency, methods for determining it, and opportunities for improvement.

Social philosophy and labor efficiency in the economy are characterized as a concept reflecting the level of labor efficiency. It sometimes applies to the labor process carried out in an enterprise or organization, and - to the process of social production that takes place in society. There are specific methods for measuring labor productivity in these subjects. Economists initially determined the efficiency of labor on the scale of an enterprise or industry, region or country, depending on the amount of production produced over a certain period of time. But with the intensification of scientific research on meow-zu, the methodology for determining labor efficiency also began to improve. Today it is determined not only depending on the amount of products produced, but also on its quality, labor costs for the production of products, the amount of income from the mecca-sulotka trade.

When discussing the level of labor efficiency, ways to increase it, scientists-economists apply the tone "efficiency of active labor," "efficiency of cash labor," "potential labor efficiency." It's no coincidence. Since, for example, the concept of "efficiency of active labor"

allows you to reflect labor productivity at the enterprise or in the industry (as on a universal human scale). In thematic sources, it is proposed to determine the effectiveness of active labor according to the formula:

$$Pe = Vp / Pc,$$

at the same time: Pe – labor efficiency; Vp – volume of production; Pc – product costs.

However, the initial goal is not simply to calculate the quantity of products produced per unit of time. Labor is associated with finding ways to increase it, unrealized opportunities. And for this, if cases of unsuccessful use of working time and labor resources are suppressed, it is necessary to analyze from the very beginning how many products can be produced under existing conditions. It is this calculation result that is expressed using the concept of "cash efficiency." In other words, the efficiency of cash labor is a unit indicating the volume of products that can be produced under existing conditions with the use of all opportunities. One of the founders of English cybernetics, economic cybernetics Anthony Stafford in his article "Cybernetics and Management" recognizes the difficulty of determining the effectiveness of cash labor using the formula: at the same time Ecp – efficiency of cash product; $Mvep$ – maximum volume of products that can be produced under existing conditions; Pe/min – minimum labor costs required under existing conditions.

As for the concept of "potential labor efficiency," it is used in economic cybernetics to reflect how much products can theoretically be produced, relying on the conditions that exist in the modern period of social development. The potential indicator of labor joy determines how much you can hope for an increase in labor productivity. Scientific sources note that the decrease in the discrepancy between the current indicator of labor efficiency and the indicator of the effectiveness of cash labor depends on a number of factors. These factors include:

- rational and efficient use of the existing material and technical base and production capabilities, steady diversification of production - as a result of which not only the volume and quality of production of products, but also its types will increase;

- introduction of innovations into production - as a result of which the entry of new scientific developments into production will be accelerated, the material and technical capabilities of the facility will be steadily improved, modern production technologies will be mastered, which will ultimately contribute to improving labor efficiency;

- scientifically sound, rational organization of the production process - as a result of which it will be possible to identify new potential opportunities for preparing better products, increasing labor efficiency with lower labor costs;

- reduction of work time losses - as a result of this, time will be saved for the performance of labor-intensive and unnecessary labor operations, performance of labor-intensive, unnatural actions, increase of labor productivity;

- development of skills and skills of employees - as a result, a certain balance is achieved between the qualifications of employees and the steadily expanding volume of professional knowledge, and the increase in qualified workers ultimately has a serious impact on the quality of work;

- improvement of working conditions - as a result, on the one hand, the possibilities of qualitative adaptation of labor functions are expanded, and on the other hand, the employee begins to receive satisfaction with his work, both cases are manifested in labor productivity;

- The introduction of a rational regime of work and mercy - as a result of which the possibilities of preserving the health of employees, the realization of their labor abilities are expanded, and an employee with good health and clearly showing his abilities becomes a factor in increasing labor efficiency;

-introduction of a system of fair remuneration - as a result, the employee's interest in the product of his own work increases, he is inclined to high-quality implementation of his tasks, his steady improvement;

-improving the psychological environment in the labor team - at the same time, healthy relations between team members are formed, these relations strengthen mutual understanding and benevolence, in these conditions the employee can competently and efficiently perform his labor functions;

-stimulating the creative activity of team members - as a result, on the one hand, innovations will increase, which can be introduced into production, on the other hand, the employee's interest in labor activity will increase.

Taking into account these factors, the efficiency of the labor of enterprises and organizations is gradually increasing in an organized society. Neglect of these factors, the use of repressive or voluntary methods instead leads to deplorable consequences. This can be seen on the example of the Soviet experience of the last century. During the years of Soviet power, labor efficiency for a long time was ensured by fear, pressure, and compulsory labor. In particular, the construction of the White Sea Canal, the construction of the Baikal-Amur Railway, the development of arid lands is a symbol of the efficiency of labor activity implemented on the scale of society, and the implementation of five-year plans in four or even three years is presented in the form of the enterprise's labor harvest. In fact, these were all labor products created on the basis of obligation. Directly, at the beginning of Soviet rule, he sought to organize these events on the principles of volunteerism. So, on April 13, 1932, a government decree "On the construction of the Baikal-Amur Railway" was adopted and began to be executed. The decree provides for the involvement of citizens of the country in construction in exchange for economic and financial incentives. However, the severity of working conditions in the taiga, food shortages, and a shortage of labor weapons led to an outflow of labor to other mines. Judging by the data, due to heavy dogs in one situation, when BAM needed 12 thousand landowners, only 504 people worked, instead of 2389 drillers - 50 people, instead of 5101 - 498 people. Then the government decided to apply the principle of obligation in the construction of the BAM and transferred it to the OGPU (state department for the protection of state security). The department immediately organized the Baikal-Amur camp and as soon as possible involved 32,411 prisoners in the construction of the highway. Thus, during the construction of BAM "labor productivity is ensured." Since the 60s of the XX century, the practice of ensuring labor efficiency through compulsory labor has decreased. Since that time, the desire to ensure labor productivity in exchange for socialist labor relations began in society. However, unfortunately, this relationship also failed to ensure labor well-being. The administrative and administrative approach did not allow enterprises to independently strengthen the material and technical base, diversify production, and introduce innovations into production. Their main task was limited to full adaptation of the plans outlined above. The workflow was also organized without taking into account the specifics of various regions. As a result, the working time was completely spent. The situation was further aggravated by the failure to comply with the system of fair remuneration, the lack of

stimulation of the creative activity of members of various teams. As a result, the level of labor efficiency in all enterprises and organizations decreased.

The economic reforms carried out in Uzbekistan during the years of independence created opportunities for improving labor efficiency in society. In particular, in the first years of independence, "strategic goals in the field of economic reform were determined: The gradual formation of the economy of a socially oriented market, the creation of an economic system that ensures powerful and strict development, the growth of national wealth, the necessary conditions for the life and activities of people.

Creating a multidisciplinary economy, ensuring state protection of private property, which is the basis for eradicating the deprivation of human property, developing initiative and initiative by all measures. Granting broad economic freedoms to enterprises and citizens, refusal of direct state intervention in their economic activities, elimination of administrative and administrative methods of economic management, widespread use of economic factors and stimulating funds. Deep structural changes that ensure the effective use of material, natural and labor resources in the economy, the production of competitive products, and accession to the global economic system. The formation of new economic opinions among people, a change in their worldview, the ability for everyone to independently determine the spheres and forms of spending their work. "

These measures had a significant impact on the level of labor efficiency of enterprises and organizations. It is for this reason that gross domestic product began to grow in the country, the volume of national economy and industrial production expanded. The reforms implemented in recent years within the framework of the Action Strategy and the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan have given a tendentious nature to the development of these factors. Thus, over the past five years, special attention has been paid to the development of the non-state sector in the structure of the economy, reducing direct government intervention in the activities of enterprises and organizations. As a result, the norm of economic freedom of subjects has significantly increased. Economic freedom, on the one hand, contributed to a sharp increase in the number of business entities and small businesses. In particular, in 2016 there were 207,104 business entities in the country, by 2022 their number reached 517 thousand 501. On the other hand, thanks to economic freedom, the efficiency of the work of enterprises and wheelbarrows has increased. Thus, in 2005, the share of business entities in the country's GDP amounted to 38.2 percent, by 2022 this figure amounted to 51.8 percent. However, it does not follow from this that the country's enterprises have taken all measures to reduce the discrepancy between the current labor efficiency indicator and the cash labor efficiency indicator. Until now, a number of problems remain in society that impede the improvement of labor efficiency. Expecting to resolve issues related to the development of the material and technical base of enterprises and organizations, diversification of development, introduction of innovations in production, organization of the production process on a scientific basis, reduction of losses of working time, identification of knowledge and qualifications of employees, implementation of a system of fair remuneration. Successful resolution of these issues would improve the labor efficiency of enterprises and organizations.

Summing up, labor efficiency is a powerful factor that can ensure sustainable economic growth. The large-scale reforms carried out in Uzbekistan during the years of independence created real opportunities for its improvement. The task today is to take measures to

rationalize the use of these opportunities, as well as to eliminate factors that impede the improvement of labor efficiency.

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